

Response of Music Towards Ornamental Plants – A Review

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Abstract:- Music has the power to trigger a range of emotions in human and other animals; it also has some beneficial effects on plant growth. Plants respond to different types of music. They grow well when exposed to certain kinds of music whereas, there may be stunted growth with another type of music. This may differ depending upon the kind of plant species also. Some scientific researchers have proved that there is some effect of music on plant growth and this effect can be used by the farmers for better growth of plants.

I. INTRODUCTION

Sound and silence serve as the medium for the art form of music. Through the use of the components of rhythm, melody, harmony and colour which creates brilliance of expression and emotion in meaningful form. Music is sound and wave is the highest form of sound. It is structured sound produced by instruments or human voices. Plants can breathe and grow because they are living things. The ability to respond to incentives is one of life's strengths. When testing experimental treatments on sensitive creatures, complex multicellular organisms like plants are compared to humans. It is well documented to have an impact on plant growth. In addition to accelerating growth, music has a clear impact on the concentration of several metabolites, such as chlorophyll, carbohydrates, protein, etc. Plants adore music and depending on the type of music and its wavelength they will respond. It has been shown that conversing with humans can help plants grow and develop more effectively. Though little has been accomplished in this field where plants are exposed to various types of sound and the results are tracked and analysed. When studying the impact of several musical genres on plants in 1968, Dorothy Retallack discovered that plants grow well when exposed to classical music whereas, plants wither when exposed to rock music. Following these discoveries, the concept of music's impact on plants was developed. A variety of frequencies and vibrations are mixed together in music in a harmonious and coherent way. It has long been held that loud, discordant noises might affect a plant's mood, health and flowers. Soft, rhythmic music is better for a plant's growth and blooming, which might affect a plant's general health and speed of growth. On the other side, some reports claim that particular musical genres can have a negative impact on plants which may be harmful to growth of plants. Heavy metal music can be particularly destructive to a sensitive plant, even when played at low intensity.

II. HISTORY

Sir Jagdish Chandra Bose (1902) an Indian plant physiologist was one of the pioneers to study the effect of environment and music on plants and he stated that plants react to attitude with which they were nurtured and are sensitive to the external environment such as light, cold, heat and noise just like human being. These were all documented in his books "Response in the living and Non-Living" published in 1902 and "The Nervous Mechanism of Plants" published in 1926.

Joel Sternheimer (1943) developed a model tune for chalcone synthase in tomato.

Dan Carlson invented the Sonic Bloom system during the year 1960.

Dr. T. C. Singh (1962) an Indian scientist and botanist noticed that balsam plants grew 20% more in height and 72 % in biomass when exposed to music. He also found petunias and marigold flowered 2 weeks earlier than controlled plants by the effect of vibrations caused by Bharatnatyam. He also observed that there are many changes of physiological and biochemical properties of plants *i.e.*, increase in growth, metabolism, no. of stomata, increased transpiration and photosynthesis, etc.

Dorothy Retallack (1973) was a student of professor Francis Brown. She conducted detailed research on effect of music on plants and conclude continuous rock music could kill the plants. She published this whole research and it's results in her book "The sound of music and plants"

➤ *How plants can hear?*

➤ *Mechanoreceptor*

It is something in human ear that help us to detect and distinguish sound waves and help us hear music and other sounds. The effect of music on plants is unclear though some people say that if plants have mechanoreceptors, they can also be able to changes in the sound waves, like those from music. It also responds to pressure.

The pressure from the sound wave causes the medium to vibrate as it travels through a medium like air or water which is how sound is transferred. The plants might pick up

on this vibration. Although plants cannot hear music, they can feel its vibration, which causes the protoplasm in their cells to move more quickly. As a result of this stimulation, the plant's system may work better, producing more nutrients that will result in stronger and better plants.

➤ *Sound production and perception in plants*

Fig. 1:- Sound-evoked physiological reaction in plants
(Source: <https://www.frontiersin.org/>)

Figure 1(A) depicts the sound production by plants. Vibrational sound is also produced by plants through their xylem. For the reason that xylem serves as a means of transferring water in plants. In the xylem, transpiration and rehydration occurred. At some point during transpiration, the stress produced by transpiration causes gas bubbles (cavitation) to form in the xylem vessels. There is no doubt that gas bubbles attached to plant vessels can also emit sound. It has long been believed that when transpiration is reduced, audible sound is released and when transpiration is increased, ultrasonic emission is released. Additionally, sound vibration is produced as the diameter of the xylem artery shrinks.

Figure 1(B) indicates the sound perception by plants. Despite the fact that there is no visible alteration. Transcriptional and translation changes are occurred in plants exposed to sound vibration. Level of mechano-stimulus responsive signalling related redox homeostatis and defence related transcripts are changed in sound exposed plants. However, the specific organs or proteins used for sound perception have not yet been identified.

Fig. 2:- Sound wave as a plant stimulant and protectant
(Source: <https://www.frontiersin.org/>)

Figure 2 showed the artificial sound treatments can elicit diverse consequences in plants by the following ways.

1. Enhancement of seed germination and plant growth: By changing the plant growth hormone like Indole-3 acetic acid (IAA) and gibberellins, Sound promotes the plant development.
2. Induction of plant defence response against pathogens: Through the activation of the plant defence hormone, such as salicylic acid (SA) and jasmonic acid (JA), sound pre-treatment increases plant immunity against ensuing pathogen attack.
3. Induction of abiotic stress tolerance: For instance, sound therapy increases a plant's ability to withstand drought by altering the cell wall's suppleness and flexibility, which affects the plant's capacity to absorb more water.
4. Delaying ripening: The maturity of tomato fruits can be halted by sound treatments. By inhibiting the manufacture of ethylene and the expression of genes associated to signalling, ethylene production may be postponed.
5. Enhancement of photosynthetic capacity: The use of sound therapy increases the expression of genes involved in photosynthesis, including those that produce fructose 1,6-bisphosphate aldose and rubisco small subunit, which may lead to the fixation of CO₂.

➤ *Music effect on the development of plants*

1. Gene activation: Certain gene is activated by specific sound frequency which increase the growth of plant cells.
2. Effect on stomata: Sound frequency technology stimulate leaf stomata to open, thereby the plants will be able to increase its uptake of spray fertilizer and dew.
3. Effect on cell organelles: By boosting the mobility of cytoplasm inside the cell, certain frequencies cause resonance in the cell organelles of living organisms which promotes cell growth.
4. Plant hormone: In response to sound, the plant hormone gibberellic acid lengthens shoots or initiates seed germination.
5. Movement of protoplasm: The sound causes the leaves to vibrate and intensify this movement, which accelerates

the synthesis of food and nutrients and promotes the growth of healthy plants.

➤ Various types of music and their effects on plants

Various types of music effects differently to plants growth. Frequency of sound also influenced the growth of plant. Classical music may help plants to grow better, bushier and greener, healthier stems; Jazz music may accelerate growth, made plants fuller; Heavy metal music with new age and Celtic tunes increase plant mass and fruit taste; Country and western music has no effect on development; noisy rock music damage plants.

Marigold plants exposed to three types of music *i.e.*, Indian music, meditation music and noise along with control (without music). It showed similar growth patterns in the beginning but in the second week onwards marigold plants treated with light Indian music and meditation music resulted better plant growth and flowering than noise treatment [1].

➤ Frequency of sound

Fig. 3:- Ranges of Sound frequency for flora and fauna

Specific frequencies and intensities can have positive effects on various plant biological indices including seed germination, root elongation, plant height *etc.* Plant thrives when they listen to music that sits between 115 Hz to 250 Hz. Plants emit audio acoustic emissions between 10-240 Hz as well as ultrasonic acoustic emissions (UAE) within 20-300 kHz. Evidence for plant mechanosensory abilities are shown when roots are subjected to unidirectional 220 Hz sound and subsequently grow in the direction of the vibration source. According to Dan Carlson, a medley of frequencies between 3000-5000 kHz can open up the stomata of plants quicker.

Activity of SOD (superoxide dismutase) in chrysanthemum callus increased with increasing the intensity (100 dB) and frequency (800 Hz) of sound and it decreased below that range [2]. In *Dendrobium candidum*, SOD, catalase activity (CAT), peroxidase activity (POD), ascorbate peroxidase activity (APX) and malondialdehyde (MDA) content of leaves, stems and roots stimulated by sound wave with certain intensity (100 db) and frequency (1000 Hz) were elevated at varying degrees under the stress and enhanced averagely than the control group [3]. Biochemical content and activities like protein content, catalase activity (CAT),

peroxidase activity (POD) and malondialdehyde (MDA) content in *Salvia splendens* cv. Vista were observed maximum when exposed to sound wave for one month at a frequency of 1000 Hz at 110 dB intensity for one hour a day. Moreover, stem length, root length, shoot weight and shoot dry weight showed an ascending trend with an increase in intensity to 110 dB in 1000 Hz frequency as compared to control [4].

➤ Effect of different length of music on plants

In an experiment by Dorothy Retallack in 1973, she exposed three group of plants to various lengths of music. In one group she played note F for 3 hours a day and in second group she played a similar note for 8 hours a day and third group remain in silence as control. The results shown that the plants in first group which was exposed to 3 hours a day the plants grew twice as large and were twice healthy as those in music-free environment. The second group the plants died when exposed music by 8 hours a day within two weeks of experimental beginning.

➤ Positive and negative effect of music

According to Vidya Chivukula and Ramaswamy, when rose plants exposed to vedic chants for 60 minutes in the morning for a period of 62 days, it enhanced the growth in terms of plant height and increased number of flowers with maximum diameter than other types of music [5]. Application of soft melodious music for 3 hours daily for 1 month to ornamental plants *viz.*, *Tagetes erecta*, *Catharanthus roseus* and *Dendranthema grandiflorum* showed increased in plant height, number of leaves, number of flowers as well as early flower bud occurrence and flowering with music treatment than control. Moreover, ornamental plants of treated set showed increased in concentration of starch, protein and phenol than control [6].

➤ Application of music on different ornamental plants

Different types of music affect differently in which some has positive effect and some has negative effects. Plants grow faster when they exposed to music and there is less pest diseases infection as well as also influence the various metabolites concentration. It can be used as component for getting higher yield with good quality. Continuous playing of music cause noise pollution for both animal and human. Pressure level of sound is inversely proportional to the distance so that the bigger the area, the lower the intensity. Still there is much confusion and contradictions about this technology in terms of frequency and exposure time periods, which may lead to the stunted plant growth.

III. CONCLUSION

From the foregoing discussion, it can be concluded that music influences the plant growth. Sound of 100 dB intensity and 800 Hz frequency enhanced the SOD activity in chrysanthemum callus. Induction of lipid peroxidation and enhancement of antioxidant enzyme activities in *Dendrobium candidum* through sound stress helps to reduce the build-up accumulation of active oxygen species (AOS) and ultimately protects plant cells from oxidative damage. Vedic chants for

60 minutes up to 62 days enhanced the growth and flowers in rose. Light Indian music and meditation music found better for healthy growth of marigold plants. Soft melodious music for 3 hours a day for one month duration showed positive results in terms of plant growth and metabolites like starch, phenol, protein and chlorophyll content in various ornamental plants viz. *Tagetes erecta*, *Catheranthus roseus* and *Dandrenthema grandiflorum*. The sound treatment at 1000 Hz frequency with 110 dB intensity for one hour per day found better for higher MDA content and antioxidant enzyme activities with rapid vegetative growth in *Salvia splendens*.

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